

DEVELOPMENT OF NOVEL X-RAY FLUORESCENCE QUANTITATIVE METHODOLOGIES TO ANALYZE AQUEOUS AND ACID EXTRACTS FROM BUILDING MATERIALS BELONGING TO CULTURAL HERITAGE

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ABSTRACT: Energy dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectrometry (ED-XRF) is widely used in Art and Cultural Heritage for direct measurements and elemental quantification of solid samples. However, in the literature there are not works dealing with the quantitative application of ED-XRF to liquid extracts coming from samples belonging to Cultural Heritage. In this work, a novel methodology based on the use of ED-XRF spectrometry after thin film deposition on special sample retainers and a subsequent evaporation was developed to quantify light elements ($Z \leq 20$) in aqueous extracts and heavy elements ($Z > 20$) in acid extracts, coming from materials and degradation products belonging to Built Heritage (mortars, black crusts and calcium carbonate formations). For this purpose, special sample retainers were used instead of more common adsorbent filter papers. Three different ED-XRF calibration methodologies were designed as elemental quantification tools and “Green Chemistry” alternatives to conventional techniques. On the one hand, the developed external ED-XRF calibration methodology for elements with $Z \leq 20$ was proposed as an alternative to ion chromatography to obtain information about the degradation processes that are suffering the building materials. On the other hand, the external ED-XRF calibration for elements with $Z > 20$ in acid extracts was optimized as a faster and cleaner quantification alternative to Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS). Finally, with the aim to reduce the matrix effect and to improve the quantitative results for elements with $Z > 20$ in acid extracts, a novel ED-XRF calibration methodology based on standard additions was successfully designed and applied to real samples belonging to Built Heritage.

1. INTRODUCTION

The characterization and preservation of Cultural Heritage is of big importance in order to understand and maintain the human evolution and history. Science and Technology can be used (a) to determine the original material composition of the artefacts, (b) to date, (c) to evaluate the alteration processes suffered and their importance in its conservation state, (d) to diagnose old consolidation or restoration processes, (e) to give assistance to restorers, (f) to propose ways for future conservation (e.g. preventive conservation), etc.¹ All these issues are enough to keep searching and developing new analytical methodologies for the study of items belonging to Cultural Heritage.

Soluble salts are considered one of the most important deterioration factors of construction materials especially in those based on carbonate compounds as for example limestone and sandstones including carbonates as binders.^{2,3} These salts can be formed due to the ions present in the water used for the

fabrication of the mortars, cements or concretes or the ones integrated through them coming from infiltration episodes. Marine aerosol as well as atmospheric pollutants can also contribute to the formation of these salts in the external part of the materials or inside their pores.⁴ Due to the porous nature of this kind of materials, the solubilized ions penetrate and go through them. The crystallization/solubilization and freeze-thawing cycles of these salts in the porous can damage the material due to the generated physical stress.² Some of these salts can also suffer hydration/dehydration processes that can also cause mechanical damage of the material due to the salt volume change that implies these cycles.⁵ An especially hazardous salt is the presence of the system thenardite/mirabilite ($\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$) which can deteriorate the materials because of its crystallization/solubilisation cycle or because of its hydration/dehydration process.⁵ As it can be observed, it is of critical importance for the conservation state of the building materials to determine the presence of these salts on them as an indicator of the conservation state of the material. Usually

their analysis is based on a first extraction step with deionized water assisted by ultrasound-energy followed by ion chromatography (IC) determination.⁶ This technique is quite good for determining ions in aqueous solution at low concentrations (ppm or $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ levels). However, the need of continuous mobile phase flux (≈ 1.0 mL/min)^{6,7} implies a big waste of chemical solvents. In addition, the precolumn, the column and the suppressor included in the chromatograph must be also changed quite regularly if the chromatographic system is used daily.

On the other hand, microwave acid extraction of the materials followed by Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) or Inductively Coupled Plasma-Atomic Emission Spectrometry (ICP-AES) analyses are usually employed for the characterization of the acidic soluble part of building materials.⁸ This acid extraction can also be used for the characterization of black crusts, that is, gypsum patinas formed due to the interaction between the material (CaCO_3) and the SO_2 present in the atmosphere. These formations can trap carbon and metallic particles in their matrix. Other kind of formations such as a kind of calcium carbonate stalactites formed due to a dissolution/precipitation process of the carbonate based building materials or other kind of patinas are also analyzed in this way. However, the characterization of the extracts with these kinds of techniques is time consuming and implies a high investment and running costs.

Energy dispersive X-ray fluorescence technique (ED-XRF) is widely used in Cultural Heritage research area due to its non-destructive character.⁹⁻¹¹ In most of the cases this technique is used to measure directly the samples in their solid form. In addition, many works use ED-XRF to obtain just qualitative information about the samples in a comparative way^{11,12} or the semi-quantitative information obtained directly from the Fundamental Parameters quantification methods implemented on portable or benchtop ED-XRF instruments.¹³ ED-XRF has also been widely employed in the environmental research field for measuring liquid samples, especially for the determination of trace metals in water samples from contaminated areas or in waste waters after different preconcentration steps of the sample.¹⁵⁻²⁰ There are some other works dealing with ED-XRF liquid sample measurements for drug analysis in blood and urine.²¹ However, to the author knowledge there are not works in which ED-XRF is used for the elemental quantification of water soluble extracts coming from building materials as a tool to characterize the decaying extent, nor for the elemental quantification of the acidic extractable part of these building materials.

There are some problems when measuring liquids directly by XRF, because they can evaporate, stratify and precipitate.²² Direct liquid ED-XRF analyses suffer from poor sensitivity when investigating low-atomic chemical elements, because if liquids are measured directly, it is not possible to measure them under vacuum with benchtop instruments. In addition, the heating of the liquid during the irradiation can promote chemical reactions or ionization of the liquid due to the interaction with radiation.²² In order to avoid all these problems there are different alternatives for measuring liquids,^{23, 24} being one of the simplest the deposition on a thin sample support and then measure it either wet or after drying it. Drying the sample reduces even more the background due to

backscattering, as much of it is caused due to hydrogen and other low atomic elements in the matrix. Moreover, once dried the liquid sample, an improvement of the limit of detection can be achieved measuring it under vacuum.

In this work, a novel methodology based on energy dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (ED-XRF) is proposed as an elemental quantification tool after thin film deposition and evaporation, representing a “Green Chemistry” alternative for the characterization of liquid samples related to the Cultural Heritage. In order to improve the results on real samples by minimizing matrix effects, standard additions were also tested. To the author knowledge, this is the first time that this kind of calibration is applied to obtain quantitative results on these kinds of samples. The quantitative ED-XRF results were compared with the ones provided by ion chromatography (IC), ICP-MS and in some cases by ICP-AES and Flame Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (FAAS).

With this aim, different ED-XRF calibration methods were designed and verified, taking into account that, ED-XRF measurement conditions must be different for the detection and quantification of light ($Z \leq 20$) and heavy ($Z > 20$) elements. Moreover, for the liquid depositions, the use of commercial sample retainers, which allow depositing larger amount of liquids than conventional paper retainers, was tested. This is the first time that these kinds of surfaces have been proved for liquids coming from the treatment of solid samples belonging to the Cultural Heritage field. In a specific way, the developed calibration methodologies were applied for the elemental quantification of soluble salt extracts (elements with $Z \leq 20$) from different mortars and for the elemental quantification of acid extracts (elements with $Z > 20$) from different mortars, black crusts, and calcium carbonate formations (stalactites and black patinas formed over the floor) from a historical building of the beginning of 20th century with a cultural value in Getxo (Basque Country, Spain).

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Reagents and solutions

Stock solutions of 1000 mg/L of Na, Mg, P, K, Ca, V, Mn, Ni, Sr, and Pb in HNO_3 0.5 M and Al in HCl 0.5 M from Romil Pure Chemistry (Cambridge, UK); 1000 mg/L Co and Cu in 2% w/w of HNO_3 , 1000 mg/L Zn in HCl 1% w/w and 990 mg/L Ti in H_2O stabilized with HF from Fluka Analytical, Sigma Aldrich (Sant Louise, United States); 1000 mg/L of Si in $\text{H}_2\text{O}/4\%$ HF and Fe in HNO_3 from Fisher Scientific (Loughborough, UK); 5000 mg/L Ba in 2.5 % HNO_3 and As in 2% HNO_3 from Technolab (Norway) and Cr in 2% HNO_3 from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain) were used for the preparation of the multi elemental standards used for the ED-XRF calibrations curves of these elements. For the selection of the most appropriate measurement conditions a multielemental stock solution, Fluka 70008 from Sigma Aldrich (Sant Louise, United States) was used. Ultrapure deionized water for preparation of dilution of stock solutions, microwave digested samples and soluble salts extracts was obtained from a Milli-Q purifiers system (Millipore Corp., Bedford, Massachusetts).

2.2. Sample description

In this work aqueous and acid liquid extracts were analyzed. On the one hand, aqueous extracts from wall mortars

and rendering mortars over concrete and acid extracts from mortars, black crusts and calcium carbonate formations were considered. These building materials and degradation products (black crusts and other formations such as a kind of stalactites and black patinas) were sampled from Punta Begoña Galleries, a building from 1918 located in front of the sea in Getxo city (Basque Country, Spain). The building is distributed into two levels. In this work, samples from the Upper Gallery are labelled as UG and samples from the Lower Gallery are labelled as LG. When the liquid extract belongs to the extraction of building material the sample is labelled with an M (e.g. MUG or MLG) or as CLG-L when it is referred to the rendering mortar over the concrete. On the other hand, when a sample belongs to a black crust, it is labelled as BCLG or BCUG (BCER is referred to black crust present outside the Galleries, growing on an external railing of the building) and when the liquid extract comes from a calcium carbonate formation from the Lower Gallery, the samples are labelled as FLG. In Table S-1 from Supporting Information the names of the samples and their description are summarized.

2.3. Sample preparation

The water soluble extracts were obtained by mixing 0.1 g accurately weighed of each sample previously dried with 100 mL of Milli-Q water during 2 h in an ultrasonic bath.⁶ Furthermore, the acid extracts of the materials were obtained after an acid digestion of 0.5 g of sample accurately weighed in a microwave oven using 3:1 HNO₃ (69%): HCl (36%) following the EPA 3051A method.²⁵

In the case of the water extraction, the liquid samples were supposed to contain ions coming from salts composed mainly by elements with $Z \leq 20$ values such as K, Na, Ca, Mg, etc. According to this, a light elements ED-XRF calibration method for Na, Mg, Al, Si, P, K and Ca was developed for the characterization of this kind of samples. For the characterization of the acid extracts of the building materials and degradation products, the ED-XRF calibration method was designed for elements with $Z > 20$ that are usually present in these materials such as Ti, V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Sr, Pb and Ba.

Both kind of liquid extracts were measured by ED-XRF spectrometry after a liquid deposition and drying optimized procedure on special sample retainers. The sample retainers are made of an external PET ring which holds a polyester film in where an adsorbent special cellulose filter is fixed. In the cellulose filter, larger amount of liquid can be deposited comparing with the conventional filter retainers. For the acid extracts coming from real samples and their calibration standards depositions, Rigaku Ultra Carry sample retainers (Rigaku, Tokyo, Japan) for trace amounts of heavy elements in solution were used in order to measure elements with $Z > 20$. However, in the case of the aqueous extracts and its calibration standards, elements with $Z \leq 20$ were quantified using Rigaku Ultra Carry Light sample retainers (Rigaku, Tokyo, Japan). The composition of these surfaces is slightly different to the ones designed for measuring elements with higher Z values with the aim of reducing the light elements signal contribution in the blank retainers to improve in that way their detection and their subsequent quantification. These surfaces have been previously reported for the analysis of waters and TCLP extracts.^{26, 27}

2.4. Instrumentation

A S2 RANGER (Bruker AXS, GmbH, Germany) ED-XRF benchtop spectrometer with touch control was used to perform the ED-XRF calibration. This instrument is equipped with a Pd target X-ray tube (max. power 50 W) and with a XFLASH™ LE Silicon Drift Detector (SDD), ultra-thin beryllium window (0.3 μm thickness) with a resolution lower than 129 eV at Mn-K α line for a count rate of 100000 counts-per-second. The distance tube to sample is 62.1 mm and the distance sample to detector is 33.8 mm. In this LE configuration of SDD detectors the intensities for Na K-alpha and Mg K-alpha are, respectively close to 8 and 4 times higher than the intensity recorded by conventional SDD detectors. The instrument is also equipped with nine primary filters that can be used in front of the tube before X-ray beam impinges the sample surface to improve measuring conditions for the elements of interest and that can operate under vacuum conditions. With S2 RANGER, the whole area where the liquid sample was deposited can be measured because the X-ray beam can irradiate it completely. More detailed information about the equipment can be found elsewhere.²⁸ The software used to control the equipment, to build the calibrations and to perform the data treatment was SPECTRA EDX (Bruker AXS, GmbH, Germany). This software can perform the full line profile fitting, deconvolution when lines are overlapped and intensity correction for interelement effects.

The ED-XRF results obtained for the aqueous extracts were compared to the ones obtained by IC and ICP-AES. For the specific case of K additional measurements were performed using FAAS. The chromatographic analyses were carried out using a Dionex ICS 2500-pressured ion chromatograph (Dionex Corporation, SunnyVale, CA, USA) provided with exchangeable columns (Dionex IONPAC AS23 4x250 mm for anions and Dionex IONPAC™ CS12 RFIC™ 4x250 mm for cations) and exchangeable ion suppressors (Dionex AERS 500 4mm RFIC™ for anions and Dionex CERS 500 4mm for cations), a conductivity detector and an autosampler. The chromatographic peak integration and data acquisition were performed with Chromaleon 6.60-SPIA software (Dionex Corporation). The ICP-AES analysis was performed using a sequential inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometer (Liberty RL, Varian, Mulgrave, Vic., Australia) equipped with a 40 MHz free running generator, 1 kW energy radio frequency and a V-groove nebulizer. 13.5 L/min Ar plasma gas and 1.5 L/min Ar auxiliary gas rates were used for the measurements. A Varian spectra A-300 atomic absorption spectrophotometer was used for the quantification of K.

For the comparison of the acid liquid extracts ED-XRF results an Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometer (NexION 300, Perkin Elmer) working in a class 100 clean room was used. More details of the ICP-MS analysis can be found elsewhere.²⁹

3. DEVELOPMENT OF CALIBRATION METHODOLOGIES

3.1. Evaluation of measuring conditions

As mentioned before, the multielemental standard solution was used in order to select the best deposition conditions for the sample retainers and the best measurement conditions with the ED-XRF spectrometer. With this aim, three depositions of 500 μL (manufacturer recommended volume) of the Fluka 70008 multielemental stock solution were deposited over three different sample retainers and then, two of them were dried at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in an oven and the additional one under vacuum. Vacuum drying turned out to be very slow in comparison to the drying in the oven which took only 20 minutes. One of the samples dried in the oven was used to deposit again 500 μL of the Fluka stock solution with the aim to concentrate the sample. The 500 μL deposition was measured alone into the measurement chamber of the instrument and then another one positioning the sample retainer covered with a teflon scattering reduction cup, in order to verify if the teflon cup was able to improve the signal-to-noise ratio. According to this, 500 μL of the prepared standard solutions and of the acid extracts were deposited into both kinds of sample retainers (for light and heavy elements). The standards and samples deposited over the sample retainers were dried in all the cases at 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in an oven. All the standards and samples were measured by ED-XRF positioning the sample retainers into the measurement chamber and using the teflon scattering reduction cup covering them. Multi elemental standards for the calibration were prepared at different concentrations in Milli-Q water, covering for each of the elements the expected concentration range in the samples, according to previous analyses of the samples by conventional analytical procedures (e.g. IC and ICP-MS).

3.2. Calibration method for elements with $Z \leq 20$

The calibration standards used for the quantification of the elements with $Z \leq 20$ on the aqueous extracts were measured under vacuum, at 20 kV, 2mA and without using any primary filter between the X-ray tube and the sample. All the calibration curves were built using the SPECTRA EDX software both for the calculation of corrected net intensities of each element lines (K_{α} or L_{α} . See Table 1) and for the definition of the calibration curves parameters.. Variable alphas model was used for weak absorption corrections and secondary fluorescence effects together with different line overlap corrections depending on the element to be calibrated (see Table S-2 from supporting information). The XRF lines selection for obtaining the calibration curves, the absorption type correction and the line overlap corrections applied (showed in Table S-2) were the ones leading to the best linear calibration curve for each of the calibrated elements.

In Table S-3 from supporting information the concentration ranges proposed for each of the calibrated elements with $Z \leq 20$ can be checked. The highest concentration calibration point was in all the cases selected according to the highest concentration expected in the samples under study and no problems were found in order to achieve the linearity of the calibration curve for all the elements. In Figure 1, examples of the calibration curves achieved for some of the calibrated elements (Mg, Al and Ca) are presented. The concentration units in % shown in Figure 1 are relative to the fact that the cellulose composing the sample retainers was introduced to the software as the main component. In this figure, the squares represent the value of the net intensities whereas the crosses

represent these values after the application of the corrections. On the other hand, the lowest concentration point was limited by the Limit of Detection (LOD) of the technique, which for the case of elements with low Z value is already high (e.g. Na and Mg). In all the calibration curves a blank (the sample retainer without adding any element) was measured and all the calibration points under the XRF signal of the blank were automatically removed. Especially in the case of Na, Mg and Si, the blank presented a high XRF signal. In addition, Na is interfered by the Pd-tube XRF lines. This interference is coming from the escape peak of the Pd L_{α} line reaching the detector, the difference between the energy of this line (2.837 KeV) and those from the Si K_{α} of the detector (1.74 KeV) is 1.1 KeV, which is close to the Na K_{α} energy. The only case in which the lowest point was selected according to the lowest concentration expected in the samples was Ca, whose concentration was very high in all the samples. Besides, the Ca calibration range was quite wide, but the linearity was maintained for all the range.

Figure 1. Calibration curves for some elements with $Z \leq 20$ (Mg, Al and Ca) and for some elements with $Z > 20$ (Fe, Zn and Pb).

The LOD for each of the elements was calculated by measuring spiked Milli-Q water with known concentrations of the elements and spiked aqueous extract sample in order to check the matrix effect. In this case, an aqueous extract from a wall mortar (MLG, the one with the lowest concentration of elements) was spiked with known concentrations of the calibrated elements. The theoretical LODs for the elements in the spiked Milli-Q water and in the spiked aqueous extract sample were calculated according to the following expression:

$$\text{LOD} = \frac{3 \cdot C \cdot \sqrt{\text{background}}}{\text{Net Intensity}} \quad (\text{eq.1})$$

Where C is the real concentration and the background intensity is obtained from the spectra. In the eq.1, the net intensity was obtained subtracting the background (counts) to the element peak intensity (counts). For all the elements with $Z \leq 20$, K_{α} lines were used. The LODs from the spiked Milli-Q water and for the spiked aqueous extract one were quite similar (see

Table 1). In order to verify if these LODs could be improved, a third experiment with the spiked Milli-Q water was performed. In this case, 1.5 mL of spiked Milli-Q water was deposited on the retainer by depositing three times 500 μ L and drying after each deposition. For this kind of aqueous extracts with low concentrations of elements with $Z \leq 20$, the effect of depositing 1.5 mL, instead of the 500 μ L recommended by the sample retainers supplier, seem to improve the LODs for all the elements with the exception of Si whose LOD was similar for both volume depositions (see Table 1). Although the deposition of 1.5 mL of sample in the sample retainer requires longer time to prepare due to the drying times in the oven after each 500 μ L deposition, both methodologies will be compared due to the improvement in the LODs.

Table 1. Limits of Detection (LODs) for elements with $Z \leq 20$ and $Z > 20$, obtained from the spiked Milli-Q water ($S_{\text{Milli-Q}}$) with the known added concentrations for 500 μ L and 1.5 mL volume depositions respectively, the spiked aqueous extract sample (MLG) and for the three different spiked acid extracts samples (MUG4, FLG4 and BCER).

Elements	500 μ L spiked Milli-Q (mg/L)	1.5 mL spiked Milli-Q (mg/L)	Spiked MLG (mg/L)	Spiked MUG4 (mg/L)	Spiked FLG4 (mg/L)	Spiked BCER (mg/L)
Na (K_{α})	9.72	4.66	11.36	-	-	-
Mg (K_{α})	4.37	2.20	3.99	-	-	-
Al (K_{α})	3.14	1.13	2.32	-	-	-
Si (K_{α})	1.19	1.58	2.64	-	-	-
P (K_{α})	1.04	0.38	0.76	-	-	-
K (K_{α})	1.76	0.91	1.27	-	-	-
Ca (K_{α})	3.62	1.19	2.30	-	-	-
Ti ($K_{\alpha 1}$)	5.42	-	-	5.07	5.57	6.10
V ($K_{\alpha 1}$)	4.84	-	-	4.20	5.13	5.16
Cr ($K_{\alpha 1}$)	3.29	-	-	3.48	4.26	4.53
Mn ($K_{\alpha 1}$)	3.44	-	-	3.03	3.59	3.95
Fe ($K_{\alpha 1}$)	1.31	-	-	3.50	3.24	4.44
Co ($K_{\alpha 1}$)	2.56	-	-	1.59	2.17	1.83
Ni ($K_{\alpha 1}$)	2.40	-	-	1.89	2.04	2.38
Cu ($K_{\alpha 1}$)	1.99	-	-	1.56	1.76	1.78
Zn ($K_{\alpha 1}$)	1.92	-	-	1.80	1.79	2.01
As ($K_{\alpha 1}$)	1.38	-	-	1.11	1.33	0.53
Pb ($L_{\alpha 1}$)	1.31	-	-	1.43	1.46	2.47
Sr ($K_{\alpha 1}$)	4.62	-	-	4.05	4.07	3.98
Ba ($L_{\alpha 1}$)	7.81	-	-	6.18	10.84	9.04

The LODs for all the spiked samples were calculated considering 500 μ L of volume deposition.

The relationship between the Limit of Quantification (LOQ) and the LOD is 3.3.

It must be highlighted that the theoretically calculated LODs according to the background and to the net intensity signals of each of the elements were far away from the real ones in the case of Na. For this element, the first calibration point that could be measured was 48 mg/L. Prepared standards under this concentration showed intensities similar to the blank. The theoretically calculated LODs for Mg and Al were

a little bit higher than the first calibration points, however when the calibration was performed, these first calibration points were already above the measured blanks.

3.3. Calibration method for elements with $Z > 20$

The best instrumental conditions for measuring the standards for the calibration method of elements with $Z > 20$ were 40 KV, 1.25 mA, using a 500 μ m Al filter between the sample and the X-ray tube and vacuum. Each calibration curve was built using the SPECTRA EDX software considering the net counts of their corresponding K_{α} line, except for the case of Pb and Ba. In this case, their calibration curves were built using the net counts of their corresponding L_{α} lines. In the same way that for the elements with $Z \leq 20$, variable alphas for absorption corrections were used for all the elements together with the corresponding line overlap correction for each element. In Table S-2 from supporting information, the applied line overlap corrections to obtain the best linear calibration curve for each element are shown.

Once the best calibration curve for each element was obtained, a method for routine spectra evaluation and quantitative analysis was generated using the software implemented in the ED-XRF spectrometer and then, the samples deposited in the sample retainers were measured using the developed quantification method.

The calibration ranges prepared for the elements with $Z > 20$ are collected in Table S-4 from supporting information. Most of the elements were calibrated between 0.1 and 10 mg/L, except the ones that were known to be in higher concentrations in the samples under study. In these cases, additional standards were measured to cover properly the wider interval. In Figure 1, some calibration curves (Fe, Zn and Pb) can be observed. In the same way that the calibration of the elements with $Z \leq 20$, the % concentration values represented in Figure 1 are the ones relative to considering that cellulose was the main component of the sample retainer.

The LODs were also calculated in spiked Milli-Q water with known added concentrations of the elements (7 mg/L). With the aim to evaluate the LODs in a more similar matrix to the samples, three different acid extract samples were spiked with known concentrations of the elements, one representing the matrix of a mortar acid extract (Spiked MUG4), another one representing the formation acid extract matrix (Spiked FLG4) and finally one as representative matrix of a black crust acid extract (Spiked BCER).

The LODs for the spiked Milli-Q ($S_{\text{Milli-Q}}$) and for the spiked acid extract samples were calculated using eq. 1. For the case of the spiked Milli-Q water, the used concentration was the added real one, while for the spiked acid extract samples, the concentration used was calculated by the addition of the spiked concentration to the concentration previously determined by ICP-MS. The XRF lines used for each of the elements for the LOD calculations and the obtained LODs are shown in Table 1.

As it is shown in Table 1, the LODs are quite similar for all the sample matrices, but depending on the element the

LODs are a little higher or lower in one or another kind of sample matrix. With the aim to improve these LODs, a pre-concentration procedure was carried out by depositing 1.5 mL of sample on each sample retainer, instead of the recommended 500 µL. However, in this case the high acid concentration caused the dissolution of the sample retainer as well as the precipitation of high amounts of solid making impossible to measure the samples. For this reason, a volume of 500 µL was used in further experiments.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Application to liquid extracts coming from samples belonging to the Cultural Heritage field

4.1.1. Quantification of elements with $Z \leq 20$ in aqueous and acid extracts

In Table 2, the elemental characterization performed using the ED-XRF methodology for elements with $Z \leq 20$ for two different aqueous extracts from two different rendering mortars over the concrete belonging to the ceiling of the lower Gallery (CLG-L2 and CLG-L4) are shown. In this kind of samples, the elements were present in very low concentrations. Considering that the calculated LODs with the spiked sample were better depositing 1.5 mL, it was decided to compare the quantitative results when depositing 500 µL and 1.5 mL of sample on the retainers. These results, shown in Table 2, are expressed as the mean value of three different replicates together with their confidence intervals at 95%.

Table 2. Aqueous extracts quantification results using the developed ED-XRF calibration methodology for elements with $Z \leq 20$ and comparison with the IC and ICP-AES values.

Sample	Element	ED-XRF 500 µL (mg/L)	ED-XRF 1.5 mL (mg/L)	IC (mg/L)	ICP-AES (mg/L)
CLG-L2	Na	1.0 ± 0.2	0.30 ± 0.01	0.38 ± 0.02	0.26 ± 0.02
	Mg	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.13 ± 0.02	<LOQ
	Al	<LOQ	<LOQ	x	<LOQ
	Si	1.4 ± 0.3	0.9 ± 0.1	x	0.16 ± 0.01
	P	3.8 ± 0.7	0.73 ± 0.05	x	<LOQ
	K	<LOQ	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.15 ± 0.01
	Ca	28 ± 5	20 ± 1	34 ± 1	28 ± 1
CLG-L4	Na	1.2 ± 0.2	0.73 ± 0.05	0.36 ± 0.06	0.18 ± 0.03
	Mg	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.18 ± 0.01	<LOQ
	Al	<LOQ	<LOQ	x	<LOQ
	Si	5 ± 1	3.0 ± 0.4	x	2.84 ± 0.06
	P	7 ± 1	3.1 ± 0.1	x	1.8 ± 0.1
	K	<LOQ	<LOQ	0.57 ± 0.01	0.59* ± 0.02
	Ca	22 ± 5	10.7 ± 0.5	16 ± 1	13.56 ± 0.08

*Concentration obtained using Flame Atomic Absorption Spectrometry (FAAS)

<LOQ → Under the Limit of Quantification

In Table 2 it can be appreciated that the obtained concentrations for the lightest elements in low concentrations (e.g Na) were improved when 1.5 mL were deposited instead of 500 µL. This fact was probably due to the observed decrease in the LOD (see Table 1) when the deposited volume was increased. However, for the quantification of Ca, which was present in a much higher concentration, the deposition of 1.5 mL in the carrier got worse the accuracy of the Ca ED-XRF result according to the IC and ICP-AES values. It must also be pointed out that ED-XRF quantification was able to give an estimation of Si and P concentrations, elements that cannot be measured by IC.

As the concentrations in the aqueous extracts were very low, in order to test the usefulness of the ED-XRF quantification methodology for elements with $Z \leq 20$, 500 µL of some of the acid extracts were deposited in their corresponding sample retainers for elements with $Z \leq 20$. As these samples have acid pH, as it was mentioned above, it was not possible to deposit 1.5 mL. In the acid extracts, it was supposed to be higher concentrations of these elements than in the water soluble salt extracts. With this aim, three different acid extracts were evaluated: one mortar (MUG1), one formation (FLG4) and one black crust acid extract (BCLG4). These samples were chosen because they have the highest concentrations of the elements with $Z \leq 20$. In this case, the obtained results were compared with those provided by ICP-MS (see Table 3). The results are expressed as the mean value from three replicates with their confidence interval at 95%.

Table 3. Quantification of elements with $Z \leq 20$ in acid extracts by the ED-XRF external calibration method and their comparison with the ICP-MS results.

Samples	Elements	ED-XRF (mg/L)	ICP-MS (mg/L)
MUG1	Na	<LOQ	<LOQ
	Mg	31 ± 7	41 ± 4
	Al	4 ± 1	7 ± 2
	Si	<LOQ	N.M
	P	<LOQ	N.M
	Ca	3200 ± 700	3600 ± 160
FLG4	Na	16 ± 3	15 ± 4
	Mg	32 ± 3	38 ± 3
	Al	8 ± 3	13 ± 7
	Si	7 ± 1	N.M
	P	<LOQ	N.M
	Ca	3600 ± 800	3400 ± 600
BCLG4	Na	10 ± 2	24 ± 13
	Mg	43 ± 2	40 ± 8
	Al	37 ± 3	30 ± 4
	Si	2.0 ± 0.3	N.M
	P	<LOQ	N.M
	K	22 ± 9	11 ± 4

	Ca	1900 ± 400	2400 ± 400
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N.M → Not Measured

<LOQ → under the Limit of Quantification but over the LOD. The relationship between the LOQ and LOD is 3.3.

Depending on the acid extract, the elements with $Z \leq 20$ were still in low concentrations, however when they were in a higher concentration as Mg in BCLG4, the confidence intervals obtained by the ED-XRF external calibration and by ICP-MS were overlapped (see Table 3). The same tendency was observed for Na in FLG4 and BLCG4. In this case the confidence intervals were wide because the Na concentration was close to the quantification limit. In fact Na in MUG4 could not be quantified by ICP-MS, but it was quantified in BCLG4 with a high standard deviation because the concentrations in both samples are very low. In this case, in the acid extracts, the concentration of Ca was much higher than in the aqueous extracts. Although this element concentration in all the extracts (see Table 3) was out of the calibration range, the extrapolated concentrations together with their respective confidence intervals overlapped with the ones obtained by ICP-MS. In fact, even though the Ca concentration is out of the calibration range, the accuracy when determining its concentration in the acid extract, BCLG4, or when determining it in the aqueous extract CLG-L4 (1.5 mL deposition), it is almost the same. This experimental evidence suggests that at Ca concentrations higher than the upper limit considered in this work, the linearity of the calibration curve for this element will be maintained.

4.1.2. Quantification of elements with $Z > 20$ in acid extracts

In Tables 4-6 some of the quantitative results as mean value from three different replicates and a confidence interval at 95% obtained from elements with $Z > 20$ in acid extracts from different kind of samples (mortar MUG4, calcium carbonate formation FLG6 and black crust BCER) are summarized.

The obtained calibration curves (see the ones of Fe, Zn and Pb as an examples in Figure 1) and thus, the external calibration methodology for elements with $Z > 20$ in acid extracts, were considered good enough to obtain accurate quantitative values. The problem in most of the cases was that the concentrations of the elements in the samples were very low for XRF technique considering its common limits of detection. As it can be appreciated in Tables 4-6, the concentrations obtained for Ti, V, Cr and Mn were under the limit of quantification. In the case of Co and Ba, the calibration methodology provided concentration values, but far away from the values provided by ICP-MS. The concentration values of Co and Ba in all the samples were under the calculated LODs (see Table 1) according to the determined concentrations by ICP-MS. The As concentration in the black crust was also calculated by the external ED-XRF quantification methodology but the concentration was not very accurate in comparison to the value given by ICP-MS. In this case, the concentration was over the calculated LOD in the black crust matrix (see Table 1), but it is still under the LOQ. The confidence interval of Pb in the mortar overlapped with the one obtained by ICP-MS. As an exception, in the acid extract from the black crust, the standard deviation was lower and the confidence interval overlapped with the one obtained by ICP-MS. The quantification of Sr was acceptable according to the concentration range at which

this element was present in the acid extract samples. Considering that in some cases the high standard deviation values and the limited accuracy obtained could be due to the matrix effect, it was tried to correct it using a standard addition calibration methodology, one for each kind of acid extracts (mortars, calcium carbonate formations and the black crusts).

Table 4. Concentrations obtained using different ED-XRF calibration approaches for acid extracts from mortar sample MUG4.

Elements	ED-XRF External Calibration (mg/L)	ED-XRF Standard Additions (mg/L)	ICP-MS (mg/L)
Ti	<LOQ	0.19 ± 0.05	0.25 ± 0.02
V	<LOQ	0.20 ± 0.08	0.33 ± 0.03
Cr	<LOQ	0.31 ± 0.09	0.17 ± 0.02
Mn	<LOQ	2.4 ± 0.1	2.7 ± 0.1
Fe	130 ± 30	N.C	130 ± 20
Co	18 ± 7	N.C	0.027 ± 0.001
Ni	<LOQ	0.07 ± 0.03	0.08 ± 0.04
Cu	<LOQ	0.44 ± 0.08	0.07 ± 0.04
Zn	2 ± 1	1.9 ± 0.2	3 ± 1
As	<LOQ	0.04 ± 0.02	0.09 ± 0.06
Sr	14 ± 5	10.0 ± 1.2	11 ± 1
Ba	100 ± 5	0.48 ± 0.08	0.68 ± 0.03
Pb	2 ± 1	1.8 ± 0.2	1.9 ± 0.3

<LOQ → under the Limit of Quantification

N.C → Not calibrated

Table 5. Concentrations obtained using different ED-XRF calibration approaches for acid extracts from calcium carbonate formation sample FLG6.

Elements	ED-XRF External Calibration (mg/L)	ED-XRF Standard Addition Calibration (mg/L)	ICP-MS (mg/L)
Ti	<LOQ	3.2 ± 0.4	3 ± 1
V	<LOQ	0.60 ± 0.05	0.6 ± 0.1
Cr	<LOQ	0.32 ± 0.03	0.38 ± 0.02
Mn	<LOQ	5.7 ± 0.8	5.0 ± 0.6
Fe	250 ± 15	N.C	260 ± 10
Co	40 ± 10	N.C	0.05 ± 0.02
Ni	<LOQ	0.24 ± 0.07	0.3 ± 0.2
Cu	4 ± 3	2.8 ± 0.8	1.9 ± 0.2
Zn	14 ± 6	12 ± 2	14 ± 7
As	10 ± 4	3.0 ± 0.7	1.7 ± 0.2
Sr	23 ± 9	14 ± 4	20 ± 5
Ba	220 ± 20	5.4 ± 0.8	7 ± 1
Pb	20 ± 6	11 ± 4	17 ± 3

<LOQ → under the Limit of Quantification

N.C → Not calibrated

Table 6. Concentrations obtained using different ED-XRF calibration approaches for acid extracts from black crust sample BCER.

Elements	ED-XRF External Calibration (mg/L)	ED-XRF Standard Addition Calibration (mg/L)	ICP-MS (mg/L)
Ti	<LOQ	1.9 ± 0.3	2.2 ± 0.3
V	<LOQ	0.24 ± 0.09	0.50 ± 0.06
Cr	<LOQ	0.26 ± 0.1	0.50 ± 0.2
Mn	<LOQ	3.7 ± 0.5	4.5 ± 0.4
Fe	250 ± 90	N.C	290 ± 40
Co	8 ± 1	N.C	0.032 ± 0.006
Ni	<LOQ	0.35 ± 0.06	0.30 ± 0.04
Cu	2 ± 1	3 ± 1	1.4 ± 0.3
Zn	8 ± 2	6.9 ± 0.9	6.9 ± 0.7
As	15 ± 7	2.5 ± 0.8	1.27 ± 0.03
Sr	4 ± 2	4.6 ± 0.6	5 ± 4
Ba	56 ± 5	3.5 ± 0.9	2.8 ± 0.5
Pb	32 ± 10	43 ± 8	31 ± 5

<LOQ → under the Limit of Quantification
N.C → Not calibrated

4.1.3. Standard addition calibration procedure as an alternative to improve the quantitative results for elements with $Z > 20$

The same sample preparation was used for the development of the standard addition calibration methodology. The only difference with the external calibration was the preparation of the standards. In order to evaluate the possible matrix effect on different kind of extracts, known concentrations of the elements were added to each different matrix (e.g. MUG4 mortar acid extract, BCER black crust acid extract and FLG6 calcium carbonate formation acid extract). In all the cases, the sample volume was 4 mL and the total volume of the added standards was less than 1 mL. Then the spiked sample was taken to a total volume of 5 mL using Milli-Q water. For the addition of the standards, different multielemental intermediate solutions were prepared.

In Tables S-5 to S-7 from supporting information section, the added concentrations of each element to each calibration point are collected. Co element was not considered in this calibration methodology since its concentration in the samples was very low. The Fe was neither added because its concentration in the samples was too high and thus the volume to be added to the sample was too high. The standard addition for this element should be performed separately to the rest of the elements. The standard addition solutions were measured using the same procedure applied to the external calibration methodology for elements with $Z > 20$. The net intensity given by this quantification method for each of the standards was represented against the added concentration. The element concentrations present in the acid extract samples were calculated according to the expression (Concentration = intercept/slope). Then, the corresponding dilution factor

was applied to calculate the element concentrations in the final acid extract samples.

The obtained calibration curves showed a good linearity. In Figure 2, the calibration curves obtained for some elements (Mn, Zn, Pb and Sr) in acid extract from the mortar MUG4 are presented as representative examples. In general terms, the highest improvement in the calibration curves using standard additions was obtained for the mortar type acid extract (e.g. MUG4). It seems that the calcium carbonate formation and the black crust are more complex matrices making more difficult to reduce their effect.

The accuracy of the quantitative results obtained with the standard addition methodology was much better than the one achieved with the external calibration methodology. In Tables 4-6 the elemental concentrations in the samples obtained using the ED-XRF standard addition methodology in comparison to the ones achieved with the ED-XRF external calibration methodology and ICP-MS analyses are shown. The results obtained from the external calibration and ICP-MS results are expressed as the mean value of three different replicates together with their confidence interval at 95%. In the case of the standard addition calibration methodology, the standard deviation was calculated from the calibration curves, but in Tables 4-6 the concentrations are presented together with the calculated confidence interval at 95%.

Figure 2. Calibrations curves obtained for Mn, Zn, Pb and Sr following the standard addition calibration procedure in MUG4 mortar acid extract.

Although the K_{α} lines of Ti, V, Cr, Mn and Ni were observable in all kind of acid extracts using the external calibration methodology, the SPECTRA EDX software was not able to determine their concentrations. On the contrary, with the calibrations based on standard additions constructed using Excel it was possible to evaluate the concentration of these elements in all the liquid samples (see Tables 4-6). If the concentrations determined for the previously mentioned elements using the standard additions (Tables 4-6) are compared to the LODs calculated for the spiked samples using the eq. 1 (Table 1), it can be noticed that they are significantly lower. However, their signals in the spectra were perfectly detected (see Figure S-1 from supporting information) and their concentrations were able to be determined accurately using the standard addition calibration curves. Trying to explain this contradiction, new LOD values were calculated for each of the elements and matrices using the y-intercept (b_0) and its standard deviation.

tion (Sb_0) values from the corresponding calibration curves obtained with the standard addition calibration following the equation 2 (see Table S-8).

$$LOD = b_0 + 3 \cdot Sb_0 \text{ (eq.2)}$$

These values are considerably lower for elements with $Z < 29$ and Ba, than the ones calculated following the eq.1 (see Table 1 and Table S-8). The concentrations of Ti, V, Cr, Mn and Ni are closer to the LODs calculated using the standard addition calibration curves, although they are still under them, except for Ti and Ni in the black crust sample (see Table 6 and Table S-8). In any case, although the concentrations for these elements are set under the standard addition LODs, the accuracy of the results is quite good in most of the cases, if their confidence intervals are compared to the ones obtained by ICP-MS.

On the contrary, Mn concentration values are above the LODs, in contrast to the results obtained using the external calibration and they are very similar to those offered by ICP-MS.

An additional element for which standard additions improved the results was Ba. With the ED-XRF external calibration, highly overestimated Ba concentrations were obtained because this element concentration is set under the LOD in the three kind of acid extracts. For this element, the LOD was also calculated using the Ba calibration curve obtained following the standard addition calibration (see table S-8). The obtained LODs for this element and for each kind of sample were much lower to those calculated using the eq. 1 (see Table 1), being the concentration values of this element, extracted using the standard addition calibration, above the standard addition LOD in the three different matrices. Moreover, the results obtained for this element are overlapped with the ones obtained by ICP-MS for the three kinds of samples (see Tables 4-6).

Finally, elements such as Zn, Pb and Sr, which were present at higher concentrations, offered also good linear regressions using standard additions (see Figure 2) and the concentrations values obtained for the three kind of samples (see Tables 4-6) were similar to the ones provided by ICP-MS.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this work a novel application based on the use of special sample retainers to concentrate liquid extracts coming from solid samples belonging to the Cultural Heritage was successfully developed to quantify the elements present in $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ units using conventional ED-XRF spectrometry. The proposed ED-XRF quantification methodologies based on external calibrations (for elements with $Z \leq 20$ and $Z > 20$) offered calibration curves with a good linearity and the obtained concentrations were accurate enough for direct elemental quantification in liquid samples (aqueous and acids). Occasionally, the concentration of some elements with $Z \leq 20$ was not too high in aqueous extracts coming from samples belonging to Cultural Heritage field, limiting the application of the proposed ED-XRF quantitative methodology. However, this methodology was

good enough to obtain accurate results for light elements when their concentration was higher than $2\text{-}30 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ depending on the limit of quantification of each element, as for the case of acid extracts. It is necessary to remark that usually the Ca content in acid extracts coming from samples belonging to Cultural Heritage is very high, thus its quantification by ICP-MS needs an additional dilution step doubling the number of samples to be measured and therefore, the time and cost of the whole analysis. The proposed ED-XRF quantitative methodology offers a fast and accurate way for Ca quantification in acid and aqueous extracts, if its concentration is higher than $3 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. Moreover, the estimation of Ca content is good enough even if the Ca concentration in the sample is out of the calibration range. Additionally, for light elements that can be present in lower or higher concentrations, the developed ED-XRF quantitative methodology can be a faster alternative to an ion chromatographic methodology for the quantification of cations forming the soluble salts crystallized on or inside the matrix of building materials belonging to Cultural Heritage.

Regarding the elements with $Z > 20$, the ED-XRF quantitative values were improved for some elements using a standard addition methodology, demonstrating in this way that matrix effect is taking place in these kind of samples.

Finally, it can be concluded that the developed methodologies can be considered a good approach for direct quantification of liquids using X-ray fluorescence spectrometry. Unlike IC and ICP-MS, these X-ray based methodologies can be included inside the "Green Chemistry" and they are also cost effective. Moreover, liquid samples preconcentrated on the used sample retainers can be re-analyzed using other instruments and techniques. As stated in the introduction section, ED-XRF instrumentation is a common tool used for determining the chemical composition of solid materials involved in Cultural Heritage and art studies. Therefore, the presented methodologies do not imply the use of additional instrumentation for the analysis of liquid samples in the laboratories related with the analysis of samples belonging to Cultural Heritage.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website. Table S-1 to Table S-8 and Figure S-1.

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Supporting Information

**DEVELOPMENT OF NOVEL ED-XRF METHODOLOGIES TO
QUANTIFY LIGHT AND HEAVY ELEMENTS PRESENT ON
AQUEOUS AND ACID EXTRACTS RELATED TO CULTURAL
HERITAGE SAMPLES**

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Supplementary Tables: Table S-1 to Table S-8

Supplementary Figures: Figure S-1

Table S- 1. Sample nomenclature and description.

Sample Name	Sample description
CLG-L2	Aqueous extract sample from the rendering mortar layer over the concrete from the ceiling of the Lower Gallery
CLG-L4	Aqueous extract sample coming from the rendering mortar layer over the concrete from the ceiling of the Lower Gallery
MUG1	Acid extract from the wall-mortar of the Upper Gallery
MUG4	Acid extract from an additional wall-mortar of the Upper Gallery
FLG4	Acid extract from a calcium carbonate formation(degradation product) coming from the mortars of the Lower Gallery
FLG6	Acid extract from an additional calcium carbonate formation (degradation product) coming from the mortars of the Lower Gallery
BCLG4	Acid extract coming from black crusts over mortars from the Lower Gallery
BCER	Acid extract coming from black crusts over the mortar from the external railing of the construction

Table S-2. XRF lines used for each elemental calibration curve (between brackets) and line overlap corrections performed to each selected line to build the ED-XRF calibration methods for elements with $Z \leq 20$ and for elements with $Z > 20$.

Elements ($Z \leq 20$)	Line overlap corrections by Intensity	Elements ($Z > 20$)	Line overlap corrections by Intensity	Elements ($Z > 20$)	Line overlap corrections by Intensity
Na (K_{α})	Mg $K_{\alpha 1}$	Ti (K_{α})	V $K_{\alpha 1}$ Ca $K_{\alpha 1}$	Cu (K_{α})	Ni $K_{\alpha 1}$
Mg (K_{α})	Al $K_{\alpha 1}$	V (K_{α})	Ti $K_{\alpha 1}$ Ba $L_{\alpha 1}$	Zn (K_{α})	None
Al (K_{α})	Si $K_{\alpha 1}$	Cr (K_{α})	V $K_{\alpha 1}$ Mn $K_{\alpha 1}$	As (K_{α})	Pb $L_{\alpha 1}$
Si (K_{α})	None	Mn (K_{α})	Fe $K_{\alpha 1}$ Cr $K_{\alpha 1}$	Pb (L_{α})	As $K_{\alpha 1}$
P (K_{α})	Si $K_{\alpha 1}$ Ca $K_{\alpha 1}$	Fe (K_{α})	None	Sr (K_{α})	None
K (K_{α})	Ca $K_{\alpha 1}$	Co (K_{α})	Fe $K_{\alpha 1}$ Ca $K_{\alpha 1}$ *	Ba (L_{α})	Ti $K_{\alpha 1}$ Ca $K_{\alpha 1}$
Ca (K_{α})	K $K_{\alpha 1}$	Ni (K_{α})	Co $K_{\alpha 1}$ Cu $K_{\alpha 1}$	x	x

*Ca $K_{\alpha 1}$ correction for Co: the software does not allow correcting the lines with pile up and escape peaks, thus in order to correct the existing overlap of Co, in high Ca presence, Ca $K_{\alpha 1}$ information was used.

Table S-3. Calibration range for elements with $Z \leq 20$.

Elements	Calibration range (mg/L)
Na	49- 503
Mg	1.1- 101.3
Al	0.5- 19.4
Si	2- 50
P	5- 201
K	1.1- 20.5
Ca	5- 206

Table S-4. Calibration ranges for elements with Z >20.

Elements	Calibration range (mg/L)
Ti	0.1- 9.8
V	0.1- 10.3
Cr	0.2- 10.1
Mn	0.1- 51.1
Fe	0.1- 608.6
Co	0.1- 10.3
Ni	0.1- 9.3
Cu	0.1- 9.8
Zn	0.1- 98.6
As	0.1- 10.0
Pb	0.1- 312.3
Sr	0.1- 49.4
Ba	0.1- 10.3

Table S-5. Added concentrations to the mortar type acid extract sample, MUG4.

Multielemental standard prepared groups	Elements	Added concentrations (mg/L)					
		Ad. 0	Ad. 1	Ad. 2	Ad. 3	Ad. 4	Ad. 5
Group I	As	0	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.09	0.15
	Ni	0	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.09	0.15
	Cu	0	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.08	0.14
Group II	Cr	0	0.07	0.09	0.17	0.26	0.35
	Ti	0	0.08	0.10	0.19	0.29	0.39
	V	0	0.08	0.10	0.19	0.30	0.40
Group III	Ba	0	0.09	0.19	0.28	0.39	0.58
Group IV	Mn	0	1.01	1.37	1.96	3.35	5.00
	Pb	0	1.01	1.38	1.97	3.37	5.03
	Zn	0	1.01	1.37	1.96	3.35	5.00
Group V	Sr	0	8.09	10.02	12.91	14.25	17.03

Table S-6. Added concentrations to the formation type acid extract sample, FLG6.

Multielemental standard prepared groups	Elements	Added concentrations (mg/L)					
		Ad. 0	Ad. 1	Ad. 2	Ad. 3	Ad. 4	Ad. 5
Group I	Ni	0	0.18	0.28	0.37	0.56	0.71
	Cr	0	0.18	0.28	0.37	0.56	0.70
	V	0	0.18	0.27	0.37	0.56	x
Group II	As	0	0.82	0.95	1.37	1.59	5.80
	Cu	0	0.84	0.97	1.40	1.63	5.95
Group III	Ti	0	2.32	3.64	4.18	5.04	6.53
	Mn	0	2.39	3.74	4.30	5.19	x
Group IV	Ba	0	2.05	3.52	4.72	5.67	x
Group V	Zn	0	8.15	11.74	13.72	15.05	17.63
Group VI	Pb	0	8.37	11.30	14.00	15.77	30.68
Group VII	Sr	0	8.43	11.43	13.94	15.76	25.14

Table S-7. Added concentrations to the black crust type acid extract sample, BCER.

Multielemental standard prepared groups	Elements	Added concentrations (mg/L)					
		Ad. 0	Ad. 1	Ad. 2	Ad. 3	Ad. 4	Ad. 5
Group I	Cr	0	0.20	0.30	0.50	0.50	0.58
	Ni	0	0.20	0.30	0.45	0.50	0.58
	V	0	0.20	0.30	0.45	0.50	0.58
Group II	As	0	0.86	1.00	1.47	2.01	2.55
	Cu	0	0.81	0.94	1.38	1.88	2.39
	Ti	0	0.85	0.98	1.44	1.97	2.50
Group III	Ba	0	1.02	2.04	2.57	3.52	4.64
Group IV	Mn	0	2.00	3.98	5.01	6.08	8.19
	Sr	0	2.00	3.98	5.01	6.07	8.20
	Zn	0	2.00	3.95	4.98	6.03	8.14
Group V	Pb	0	4.99	9.90	20.00	30.20	35.34

Table S-8. Limits of Detection calculated according to the standard addition calibrations curves.

Elements	MUG4	FLG6	BCER
Ti	0.384	3.49	1.61
V	0.405	1.52	0.793
Cr	0.550	0.432	0.324
Ni	0.334	0.910	0.698
Ba	0.433	3.59	1.65

Figure S-1. Zoom of the spectra obtained for the addition point 1 (lowest added concentrations) for the mortar (MUG4), the black crust (BCER) and the carbonate formation (FLG6).